

ART FRONTIER

An International Art Journal / Vol.1, No.3 & No.4 Jul.-Sep., Oct.-Dec., 2023

Paul Kos with Andrew McClintock

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To cite this article: Paul Kos, Andrew McClintock, “Paul Kos with Andrew McClintock,” *Art Frontier* 1, no.3 & no.4 (December 2023): 50-63, <https://doi.org/10.64212/ZIIS1500>.

DOI: 10.64212/ZIIS1500

ISSN: 2835-5490

EISSN: 2836-841X

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This article has undergone double-blind peer review.

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Publishing Frequency: Quarterly (March, June, September, December)

Paul Kos with Andrew McClintock

On a foggy Sunday afternoon in December, Paul Kos picked me up from the SFAQ office in the Tenderloin, and we headed through the deserted streets of the Financial District in San Francisco. Our first stop was at “Poetry Sculpture Garden”, a public art piece he did with poet Robert Hass, (2000) at 199 Fremont. We then headed to the USF campus off 3rd Street in Mission Bay to check out *Everything Matters* (2011). Standing in front of the mosaic, I felt a little lost due to my red-green color-blindness problems. Finally, I came clean, which led to a color test later in the day, but it made me thankful that I wasn’t suffering from a general lack of understanding of conceptual based public art. We jumped back into Paul’s truck and drove to his studio on Potrero Hill where we sat down at his table with a big glass of beer and began our almost 3-hour conversation in which we covered Paul’s very complex and diverse conceptual art-making practice, public art, his 40 years of teaching, and a bit of art history.

ANDREW MCCLINTOCK

So let’s start with the work you were doing in the late 60’s and early 70’s that stems from driving back and forth from San Francisco to Wyoming.

PAUL KOS

Well, I was going back to Wyoming yearly for about three weeks and then taking this drive across Nevada, Utah, and Wyoming. So, I started proposing these highway sculptures, often publicly disintegrating salt sculptures. I had already done *Lot’s Wife* (1969) at Rene di Rosa’s ranch in Napa [di Rosa Foundation]. Before this, I was making fiberglass pieces for his lake to float, and I thought, how stupid I am—I had rubber gloves, a mask, a monkey suit—using all these toxic materials and resin. One day, I was looking out across his 500 acres of vineyards and cattle, a Barbizon-looking landscape, and I asked di Rosa if I could do one more piece. This was my

Figure 1. Paul Kos. 2011. Portrait by Andrew McClintock.

pivotal piece, making work respectful of the site with indigenous materials—it was the big cut.

AM

Because of the use of natural materials?

PK

Yes. I was in the main house looking out upon the fields and saw all these cows licking their salt—so it was made for them and me. It was tall because Di Rosa wanted to see it from the house—the grass was still dead where the piece was, and that much salt fries the ground. Simultaneously, I was taking these trips to Nevada and Utah, proposing these pieces to their Highway departments—they never wrote back—and I’d write again and ask them if I could do pieces along the salt flats, these early cast salt pieces were spheres (*Drawing for a Salt Sphere*, 1968). This is still a throwback to before *Lot’s Wife* when I was thinking along the same lines but using resin and salt—it led me to question: who did not use only the actual material, “salt”?

So the highway became my studio...anyway, they [Nevada Department of Highways] never wrote back, and I could have just done it, probably the amount of time, money, etc., to buy the salt blocks and leave them out there...It was nevertheless a good studio process that led to other things. Ultimately, I didn’t make any pieces besides the aluminum pieces.

AM

How big were those pieces?

PK

The boulder (*Aluminum Tertiary Strata*, 1968) was the size of a floor-to-ceiling bookcase, and I filled the pockets in the rock with tin foil. It lashed in the light and

was about 100 yards off the road. I have heard people stopped, thinking they had seen silver deposits.

AM

And the Richmond Art Center?

PK

Then I started doing [pulls out a piece of paper and a small box] pieces like *Quid pro Quo* (1970) for the Richmond Sculpture Annual, an exhibition juried by Larry Bell. In this piece, I removed the object in art. The passing of money between patron and artist became the art, process becomes art, patron becomes an artist. The artist becomes a patron. Banks become museums.

As Paul makes coffee, I am left to rummage around the pile of ephemera left on the dining room table. I pick up *Quid pro Quo* (1970).

AM

Were there many people who wrote back?

PK

I got quite a few, and I would send them back the same amount of money they sent me, and it would cost me about five dollars each because the bank didn’t want to do it since it was a custom check. Many of the checks were for small amounts, like 10 cents, which was unfortunate. Then, it was published in *Art Week*, meaning hundreds were out there. Then one day I got a knock at my door, three guys showed up in suits and hats, and my kids were little at the time, and they were like, “Daddy is going to go to jail.”

AM

Was it the postal police?

Figures 2, 3. Paul Kos. *Everything Matters*. 10'×60', 2011. Photograph by Ira Schrank Courtesy Paul Kos.

PK

The post office Department came to my home thinking that I was doing mail fraud, collecting money and not sending it back. So I showed them all of my checks received and copies of checks mailed out and it was fine. They couldn't believe anyone would do that. They were ready to handcuff me and take me in...it was scary.

AM

So even this process sculpture is outside the museum—even though it's displayed in the museum.

PK

And it went outside by reaching the newspaper. It got printed and then diluted, and finally there were so many out there that I could have gone broke if they had all been sent in. I would have had to make a deal with the bank or something.

AM

Was that your first show?

PK

No, before the Sculpture Annual, I met Tom [Marioni] at the Richmond Art Center, where he had a show called "Invisible Art". I saw it and told him what I was up to and he soon gave me a one person show there in 1969. This was the announcement [pulls out a bumper sticker that reads Participationkinetics] and you put it on your car and it became a kinetic sculpture. Now it's called interactive art, but I called it participation kinetics at the time.

The other piece I did at the Richmond Art Center was the ice piece called *The Richmond Glacier* (1969). Because it was outside, it forced the viewer to find another entrance. I was blocking the entrance with 10,000 pounds of ice. It was summer and shouldn't have lasted long but the fire department came and chopped it to pieces.

Figure 4. Paul Kos. *Drawings for a Salt Sphere* are showing three stages of erosion. Resin and salt. 1968.

AM

Why did the fire department come?

PK

Because I was blocking the entrance—major means of egress—so they just chopped it with their axes—I didn't have a video camera with me in those days and it was a mayhem—beautiful to watch—how could you get them to do such a thing for you? It was quite a scene.

Then Jens Hoffman 3 or 4 years ago invited me to a show in Sao Paulo called "This is Not a Void" and we did the same thing—but this time the ice melted in 3 to 6 hours since it was much warmer down there.

AM

What about the gel caps with Einstein's theory on rice paper?

PK

Yes, that was another one. I had *Kinetic Capsules* that the viewer could swallow, with Einstein's Theory of Relativity inside. The original also had a small ball bearing, so the piece ended when you heard a "clink" in the toilet. But the health department wouldn't let me do it because there could be someone with a low spot in their intestine, and then the ball would stay inside of them and they would have to go into surgery, so they wouldn't let me do it.

AM

How did the Health department find out about it?

Figure 5. Paul Kos. *Aluminum Tertiary Strata*. 1968. Wyoming/Colorado border: Aluminum foil, rock. Variable dimensions.

USE DOOR
TO COURT
→

MAIN ENTRANCE
RICHMOND ART CENTER

GALLERY HOURS

MONDAY ~~THRU~~ THURSDAY 9:00 A.M. - 9:30
FRIDAY 9:00 A.M. - 4:30
SATURDAY 11:30 A.M. - 5:00
SUNDAY 2:00 P.M. - 5:00
CLOSED HOLIDAYS
PHONE: 234-2397

Figure 6. Paul Kos. *The Richmond Glacier*. Installation view at the Richmond Art Center, 7,000 pounds of ice and salt blocks, 60"×60"×60". 1969. Courtesy Paul Kos.

Figure 7. Paul Kos. "Participationkinetics". Bumper sticker used as exhibition announcement. 2 1/4"x14 3/8", 1969. Courtesy Paul Kos.

Figure 8. Paul Kos. *Kinetic Capsules*. Gelatin capsules and paper, dimensions variable, 1969. Courtesy Paul Kos.

PK

Somehow, it came up that I should ask, suggested by either Tom or his boss. It would be a nice sound way to end the piece...but it didn't work. Again, that was my way of getting the viewer involved with the work.

AM

Because there wasn't a conceptual art movement or anyone showing that kind of work then?

PK

Not really, at least to my knowledge at the time.

AM

Where are you aware that this movement was starting to take place?

PK

Partly, partly not. I met Tom and Terry [Fox] later, and then Willoughby Sharp and then there was *Avalanche* magazine and that's when it became apparent. Once in a while, there would be a little thing in Art Forum and I remember writing [Leo] Castelli and trying to get something going. Ivan Karp was his director then, saying,

"By the way, do you know that the Castelli family made their fortune in salt?" I happened to be doing these salt pieces. So we started this dialogue but nothing came from it. Later, when his new director saw a video piece of mine, I ended up with Castelli for 4-5 years, but as a video artist. When he got tired of video a few years later, I had trouble convincing him that I was a sculptor who happened to use video.

AM

The video pieces during that time were "Ice Into Fire"...

PK

Yes. As well as *Tokyo Rose* (1976), I showed that at Castelli and because of it, I was invited to the Paris Biennale. They rebuilt it over there. It was great. So many people went into 420 West Broadway [Castelli's Gallery] that subsequently, you would be invited to shows in cities you have never heard of. So you are invited into this cage in Tokyo Rose, but why would you want to go in? Ah, but the voice is so seductive, "Come in...give up", and there is no payoff, but that's okay because other people are there with you.

A few other pieces involved this idea of participation that I turned into gallery and museum pieces like *Mar Mar March* (1972-73) instead of existing outside of the white cube. In *Mar Mar March*, a specific sound requires viewer participation or doesn't work. In the installation, there was a small T.V. at the end of this room, and in the 1970's that became a bait, 2x4's crossed the viewer's path spaced about a foot apart. On a typewriter, I typed the sound of a drum beat. To reach the T, V, the viewer had to step between the boards on the floor. There weren't TVs in museums then, so using it as a draw wasn't hard.

Now I want you to hear the sound of "Mar Mar March" because this is the most important of my sound pieces [Paul starts a sound recording] and my first video that wasn't a video narrative or documentation of a performance. So I'm typing "mar (space) mar (space) mar c, h, space" it sounds like "ta ta ta tum, ta ta ta tum,

Figures 9, 10. Paul Kos. *REVOLUTION: Notes for the Invasion: mar mar march*. Wood, typewriter, and video. Variable dimensions, 1972-73. Courtesy Paul Kos. (left and above)

ta ta ta ta tum”. So when you walk into the room, you’re confronted with this sound and can faintly hear it but can’t see it.

AM

And the mini TV is behind the typewriter?

PK

Yes, and as you get closer, you are stepping in between the boards and what you are doing is lifting your feet. Halfway down the room you are marching, whether you like it or not, and you can’t control it—it’s impossible, you would trip if you didn’t. So the viewer is marching to my “notes for the invasion”. And for me, that became a major piece because it’s an onomatopoeia, a piece that sounds like it looks and looks like it sounds. So if that’s public art, it was designed to be more of a museum piece—it did lead me to think of how to get the viewer involved.

AM

So sound becomes a byproduct of many of these interactive pieces.

PK

Yes. In a way it seems like an accident—because it wasn’t so much as a contrivance. In 1970, I did “rEVOLUTION”, a piece at di Rosa’s where I transferred 50 pounds of ammunition into a target. I had the ammo hung from belts on my body and I had a shotgun and I

shot into this target and that was certainly an audio piece. It was a byproduct of shooting, but I wanted to transfer weight invisibly in space from here to there. I was on a scale and the target was on a scale. The target suffered damage and my shoulder suffered damage.

AM

There was a live broadcast too?

PK

Yes, it was piped into the living room, black and white TV, live, closed circuit.

AM

It was 1970, so it was one of the first live closed circuits?

PK

Yes, and all for the audience. Tom Marioni happened to be there and Howard Junker (Founder of ZYZZYVA Magazine) was there as well and at the time he worked for Newsweek. He was the art editor.

AM

Let’s briefly talk about another ice piece you did at Marioni’s Museum of Conceptual art in 1970.

PK

Yes. I made *Sound of Ice Melting*, with the help of sound engineer, Richard Beggs. The piece consisted of two 25-

pound blocks of ice on the ground, surrounded by 8 boom microphones fed into a mixer, amplifier, and two large speakers. The thing that made this piece credible was when you'd turn up 1970s analog sound equipment, it produces a beautiful white sound that makes the viewer question if it's the sound of ice melting or an imagined sound due to the white noise. Also, Richard Beggs later won an Academy Award for Sound in Francis Ford Coppola's "Apocalypse Now". Another interesting aspect of this piece when it is shown is that the ice needs to be replaced daily and the decibel levels lower as the visual volume of the ice decreases...

AM

Let's talk about your residency at Capp St. Projects.

PK

Well, 65 Capp St. is a galvanized steel building that Ann Hatch bought and in which she started the residency program. I was invited, and since I'm a local, I didn't need the residency part, so my proposal was, "I don't have one... I will spend a month thinking of one, a month building it, a month showing it", and she agreed. The main thing that influenced me was the amount of audio graffiti, the cars, and the boom boxes in the neighborhood. The piece I did there is called *Sympathetic Vibrations* (1986).

AM

This was in 1986, so the Mission was not gentrified.

PK

No. It was the Mission. A mezzanine in the house made one half a bell curve, and I used to walk back and forth, back and forth, again waiting for an idea. Suddenly one day I heard the bells at Mission Dolores and the audio graffiti outside, and that's when I decided to do a bell piece. I had never done one before—that was the first one, and it led to many.

AM

You had different sized and weighted bells?

PK

Yes, and I didn't know how to ring them, so I brought someone out from Wyoming because when I was a kid I used to ring the big bells at church for weddings and funerals. It was fun if you got to ring the bells. So I brought the guy out who used to teach me, he would only come on a train, and he used the residency, stayed there and taught us how to ring. Now, he never taught a woman before, and he said, "...

I don't know...women don't ring bells", but he did. I rented four big bells from Cincinnati, The Verdin Bell Foundry, borrowed two from the symphony, and one or two from some friends, so I think there were eight in total, and the big one weighed 1,000 pounds.

AM

How did the residents in the neighborhood react to this?

PK

They thought it was a new church. Latino women would come in, stand around, pray, and realize that it wasn't a church, but they would still stand there praying. I think it had to do with the amount of vibrations that were being resonated in the building by the bells. You could feel it through your bones.

AM

How long was each performance?

PK

We did about three minutes per day. We were shut down one day when someone called the police. It was the last day and we rang quite a while, but there was a big football game on TV and we rang for about an hour and went into their time zone. It was our last day and we were drinking, so...

Before this, I did a piece called *Chartres Bleu* (1983-86) the stained glass window piece comprised of 27 TV/monitors turned on their sides. It's at di Rosa's permanent-ly now, in a tunnel and chapel underground that he had built for it. I made it in 1983-86 but couldn't find any place to show it. It was scheduled at SF MOMA, but the new curator that came in canceled it, and then it didn't show until 1986 when it went to the Walker Art Center. They produced it, bought all the

Figure 11. Paul Kos. *rEVOLUTION*. Performed at the di Rose Preserve, 1970. Courtesy Paul Kos.

Figure 12, 13. Paul Kos. *Sympathetic Vibrations*. Installation with eight bells at Capp St. Project, 1986. Courtesy Paul Kos.

equipment and everything. They then rented it to SF MOMA for \$16,000, so they could pay themselves back.

AM

When did you start using petanque as interactive artwork?

PK

About two years after that incident when the San Francisco Arts Commission asked if I could do a piece in their little vacant lot on Grove St., I put in a petanque court and invited people to play. Di Rosa bought one of my petanque pieces (*Zizzi Va*, 1994) and it's up at the ranch, but no one is playing so it needs to be weeded and I need to give lessons again.

AM

What are some of your favorite pieces you have done?

PK

I wouldn't say I like carpets for showing sculpture [Anglim]. My wonderful dealer has a wall-to-wall carpet in her gallery. I wouldn't say I like it. Whenever I have a show I ask if I can take it out and she says "no". So I was in a show at the Laguna Museum of Art Annex, which was in the 2nd largest shopping mall in the USA, and there was a carpet there and I asked them, "Can

I take the carpet out because it looks terrible with my sculpture" and they replied, "oh god, every sculptor asks that, if we let you do it they'll think we're favoring you because you're from the North". So I told them I wouldn't take it out, but I would do a piece with it and then they could take it out after my show. And so I did *Rift* (1990) a piece that is just like the Berlin Wall. I took the carpet, cut out a long strip, and rolled it back, and it became this thing that you had to step over. I heard at the opening one of the staff saying, "When he leaves, we are just going to glue the carpet back down." So before I left, when I still had the keys I went in one night and cut one inch off the entire length of the roll so when they rolled it down at the end of the show they had to take the whole carpet out. It was my public intervention, and now they have a beautiful concrete floor.

AM

After the Capp St. residency, bells return to your work in different forms. Let's talk about the big group show in Norway that you were in.

PK

The show in Norway was called *Neighborhood Secrets* and we were each given a building in the city of Stavanger. They gave me the cathedral, because of my past work, I didn't get the lighthouse or anything like

Figure 14. Paul Kos. *Rift*. On-site carpet (cut) 20'x24", 1990. Courtesy Paul Kos.

that. The Cathedral was built in 1198 under the direction of a Benedictine monk. In 1558 the Danish king came and stole the five big bells out of the cathedral to melt them down to make cannons so he could wage war on Sweden. He loaded the bells on a ship and he's sailing out of the harbor and a storm comes up and the ship goes down somewhere not far from Stavanger. In the 1960's, some scuba divers found an anchor where they found it and no one could dive deeper at the time. Well, since I had a budget I asked if we could get Remote Operational Vehicles (ROVs) to look for the lost bells. The group of curators assisted me in convincing the Norwegian Navy into going to search for the bells. They could only do this for two days and then had to leave for other exercises. This would otherwise have been a very costly enterprise. Then an oil company took over and they looked for a while and it made the local papers. Suddenly the town started getting excited over who would own the bells if they were found. The oil company, the historical museum, the Cathedral... they never did find them, but a video of the ROV search was made available to me.

AM

So the video and the bell you made of oil became the relics of the piece?

PK

Yes, I mean the big thing was getting the Navy to search for the bells, which were amazing. Imagine if I called up Rumsfeld?

AM

So another happy accident?

PK

Exactly. Another interesting thing about the bells because they are made of bronze is that five hundred years later they would still be intact, while their tongues [or clappers], would have rusted away because they were cast iron. So the bells would have no voice and we would have to return it to them with a new tongue.

AM

The piece seems pretty political as well.

PK

Yes, and the show as a whole ended up being a little didactic because all of the other artists had some political affiliations, but the show was set up that way. The city was informed of all of this through the newspapers beforehand. There was this pulpit in the Cathedral and they expected me to talk when the show opened. So I gave a speech about how Norway is uniquely positioned to pick and choose their oil buyer. If they don't like something politically about the country that purchases their oil, they don't have to sell it to them. The example I used is that Norway is against ever using landmines and is promoting a worldwide treaty. The US refuses to sign it, so don't sell oil to the US. I then apologized for coming from "Bush country".

AM

Earlier today we drove past a site off of 3rd Street near the ballpark where you are proposing a new public works project. Let's talk about this a little bit.

PK

The commission is for the new San Francisco Public Safety Building. If it works out, and I will know very soon—as it's been passed by the San Francisco Arts Commission. Essentially, I went around the police and fire warehouses looking for an icon... I'm waiting for that accident again. And I discovered that the SF Fire Department is the most traditional in the United States. It still uses 60-foot wooden ladders. They hand varnish them. And so the ladders and their fire trucks are impeccable. There is a big siren on every fire truck, but there is a cast bronze bell right next to it. They still

Figures 15, 16. Paul Kos. *River Wall*. 230'x30', 2010. Photograph by Eduardo Pineda Courtesy Paul Kos.

cast them in a shop, which I visited. They cherish their wooden ladders and bells. Looking for an ideal police icon was more difficult because of the nature of their work. Ultimately, I adopted their 7-point police badge, a very aesthetic, graphic symbol. Therefore, I'm proposing a twenty-thousand-pound bronze bell and a seventeen-thousand-pound black granite star. The bell will be made in France because no one in the US makes bells this large any more. It is proposed that the bell will ring every day at noon if all is well. Therefore I call the installation *The Star and the All is Well Bell*.

AM

In 2010, you finished a large commission up in Sacramento called *River Wall*. How was this experience?

PK

Susie Wallenstein, an engineer at East Bay Mud in Oakland who was part of a project where they were building a pump station on the Sacramento River along with the Sacramento Water District contacted me. Together the two entities founded the Freeport Water Authority and built a large building near an oxbow on the river, which means there is a very slow current at that site. The water swirls around slowly but doesn't go upstream or down because it's such a big bend in the river. Susie had seen the *Poetry/Sculpture Garden* and invited me to do a new piece. The wall they gave me on the pump station was 225 feet long by thirty feet high. What I did, since there isn't much current there—literally, you could throw a leaf in the water and it would stay a long time before finding its way downstream... Well, because I can write with both hands. I went to the blackboard in their office and wrote "revirriver", one forward and one backward in Palmer penmanship. They decided right then and there that they would blow it up on the wall to 225 feet, so it could be seen from Highway 5, driving south to LA. They also wanted a text related to water to be seen by viewers who visit the wall up close. I picked short quotes from John Muir, Cummings, Rebecca Solnit and many others. And I embedded them into the wall making it almost like concrete poetry. The piece can now be seen from the freeway or the walking and bike path along the river.

AM

Your recent mini-retrospective show at Gallery Paule Anglim in 2011 included some earlier conceptual drawings that also functioned as sketches for early proposals. Do you still work in this style sometimes?

PK

I don't do that as much as I used to. In the 70s, many were just shooting for the moon, even if there was a very small chance of ever completing them. But they did function as proposals as well. When doing them, I fell in love with the paper and took great care to make those drawings. Real India ink on high gloss chrome-coat paper. First, I felt art must be visual. That doesn't mean decorative, but it certainly means neither didactic, pedantic, preachy, or overtly political.

AM

So let's talk about the Bay Area as a video hub and the beginning of video as an art medium.

PK

Well, Nam June Paik had the first poat-a-pack in New York before we had one on this coast, but a guy named George Bolling [videographer for the deSaisset Art Gallery at the University of Santa Clara under the directorship of Lydia Modi Vitale] made the first videos in the Bay Area. He was one of the earliest for sure. I taught a conceptual art course at the University of Santa Clara in 1972. Seven years later, I still didn't get tenure so I started teaching at the San Francisco Art Institute. That's right around the time that Howard Fried began the Video Performance Department, later called New Genres, and in that first graduating class I had Tony Labat, Karen Finley, and others.

In one of its last years giving out individual fellowships, an NEA Panel gave 3/4 of their fellowship in New Genres in the entire USA to faculty and ex-graduates of SFAI's New Genres Department. That was a quite impressive showing.

AM

How did the San Francisco Art Institute education play into your exploration of the early conceptual movement?

PK

Well, to be quite frank I felt a little shortchanged about the education there because it didn't even consider enough contemporary art history, Pop, Minimalism, etc. It was Bay Area abstract expressionism day in and day out—do or die—and I was a good disciple. I had Diebenkorn, Bischoff, Joan Brown, Lobell, etc., and I pained enough like them so they liked my work. But then, when I left, I realized there was a whole world out there that - well, I guess I expected to be fed a little more, not self-discover everything. I had to become self-taught if I wanted to become a sculptor. Art school should accelerate a person's time spent in the studio. It should

be accelerated because you are getting constant critiques, getting fifteen peers to give you instant feedback. Even while teaching at Santa Clara University and later for 30 years at SFAI, one of my teaching techniques is never letting the student/artist speak when showing their work because we then talk about what they are saying—not the work. The work either defends itself well or does not cover everything the artist intended. Good art has good timing and good craft.

AM

Earlier today we were talking about the artist being in shape, and how this is necessary for the artist to produce good and relevant work—please talk about how this works in your practice.

PK

Well, when I get out of shape... an example is when I built the Tower of Babel—I fell out of shape. And the reason was that it took about a year and a half to make it. Most of the piece was logistics and manual labor. While doing that you're not making art, you're just doing all the things that need to get it done and I realized I wasn't thinking that much and felt naked when I finished the piece. That's when I made the broom piece (*Equilibre* 1991); I had no ideas. I was leaning on my broom and suddenly it stood up and I started doing work again. Working doesn't necessarily mean you're in shape—it's about how much thinking is going on and pushing ideas. Manual labor doesn't necessarily equal art. Bill Viola told me once that he spends four days a week with clerical work to spend one day in the studio.

AM

Let's talk briefly about your views of the function of independent art magazines.

PK

Well, one of the only reasons we know of painters like Diebenkorn, Bischoff, Joan Brown, Bruce Conner and Wiley, at least initially, is because Art Forum started here, in San Francisco. The Art Forum moved to LA and that's when we heard about artists like Robert Irwin, Larry Bell, etc. Then it moved to NYC and we stopped hearing about all those artists, leaving a vacuum on the West Coast. Then in 1977, I was invited to the Paris Biennale and stopped by the Eigervand, the famous North Face in Switzerland, thinking I would climb it one day. At the time, I couldn't name 6 contemporary Swiss artists. Then Parkett magazine appeared on the scene and changed everything. Yes, there was always the Basel Art Fair, but no one knew about the Swiss artists

of the day. Because of Parkett, dealers, gallerists, and collectors it has started paying more attention to art in Zurich in particular and Switzerland in general. What *Avalanche* magazine did for conceptual art, Parkett did for Switzerland. San Francisco is a provincial town, not because there aren't artists here; there are probably over 10,000 working artists in the Bay Area, but it is hard to get one's work out because of a lack of international media—that's why what you are doing with SFAQ is so important.

AM

Yes, and there will always be something special about printed matter and it's an integral part of capturing the "scene".

PK

Yes, I agree. In your lap, and I don't mean a laptop, a lot of art can be found.

AM

Well, it used to be more like that—artists getting subversive in the medium of print.

PK

[Stephen] Kaltenbach was the one that stated all that in 1970 "become a legend" "tell a lie" when he took out these ads in Art Forum.

AM

In the 70s, you used the game of pool in some performances, one of which was on the East Coast. Let's talk about these a little.

PK

Well, there was a famous pool hall, Palace Billiards, on Market Street in San Francisco, on the second floor with twenty-four slate tables and leather pockets, that's now sadly closed. It had great paintings of lions and jungle scenes, about 12 by 16-foot canvases, really gorgeous. There were a lot of pros playing there. So I went there for 6 months and played as often as possible. I also deducted all my receipts. The IRS subsequently audited me and said I couldn't deduct pool time. Luckily, I had a show in NYC and got a write-up in the *Village Voice* to write it off as research. That show in NYC was at Reese Palley Gallery. I went into the famous pool hall on the Lower West Side, where *The Hustler* with Paul Newman and Jackie Gleason was shot. So I went in and walked up to the guy at the front desk and asked the receptionist who was the best player in the place, to which he was a little taken aback—but he glanced at someone and so

Figure 17. Paul Kos. *Pool Hustle*. 1972. Paul Kos is on the left.

I walked over to this guy who was in a white suit like Tom Wolfe would wear. And I told him, “A Rolls Royce is waiting for you outside if you would like to play pool at an art gallery and the gallery will pay for my losses at \$5 a game”. So he walked over to his locker and got his 3 piece cue and we drove to the gallery and my opening was that same evening. The whole night I won only three games out of about 29. He managed to run the table, game after game. When I would finally be able to get a shot I would be so nervous, because I hadn’t shot in so long and if I didn’t make it work I would be dead. It was an unbelievable performance. He also had a bad leg so he walked around the table with a hobble and he would make a shot and then start bitching. “You know, here I am in this art gallery, playing for 5 dollars a game. Do you know what it takes to play this game? A beginner is 3-4 years, an intermediate is 10-12 years, and an expert like

me is 16 years. I could be a psychiatrist by now but I’m not, I’m playing pool in an art gallery!” The conversation was wonderful because as people watched, he wasn’t missing any shots. The more bitter he got, the better he got. It didn’t matter if I lost because the gallery covered my tab. People were invited to play after the opening performance and throughout the month. That piece was called *Pool Hustle* (1972). Another piece I did in that show that referenced this conflict of art and life was *Camouflage* (1972), on the wall I installed white game traps that were all set. People would test them to see if they were set by putting cigarettes into the trap and having their cigarettes cut in half. In a later show in Newport Beach, California, I put game traps on the walls again but placed a pool table near the corner right by them. If I left the cue ball on the trap side of the table and left my opponent a shot on that side, they would be

nervous because if you pushed your arm back or your elbow and weren't careful, the game traps would catch you or your cue. People wouldn't shoot as well as I... that was one of the last public pool pieces I did. I did one more at the Walter McBean Gallery at SFAI.

AM

You currently have a piece that is sheetrocked over behind one of the walls in the Walter McBean Gallery at SFAI. Does it have to do with your love of climbing?

PK

That was part of the Gargoyles series (1985). And I was again, going back to the idea of participation being one of the elements in public art, at least in my consciousness. In addition to the piece inside the gallery, I painted gothic arches on four concrete walls outside the gallery, I brought someone down from the Sierras, a master climber named Chris Vandiver. We put up these very difficult routes, marked with oil pastels, so some lines still might be there, and I invited people to come and try them. I took my class out, offered some basic climbing gear, and told all my students that whoever could climb any of the routes would get automatic honors. No one got the grade except for Dawn Fryling, a former SFAI graduate student. I even left climbing shoes in New Genres to check out in different sizes. I'm not

sure if they are still there.

Another piece from this series was in the Walter McBean Gallery, the sheetrock piece you referred to in your question, "Gargoyle VIII." I cut the sheetrock out of the gallery's west wall, making an opening in the shape of a tall gothic arch, about 20 feet high by about 3 feet wide and 18 inches deep. Knowing the "chimney" technique, you can shimmy up and down. Or if you know the "layback" technique, there was a small crack on the right side going up that you could put your fingers behind and your feet against the wall and go up. There are no holds anywhere. You either wedge yourself in the chimney or lay back the crack. So we performed the opening and then for the duration of the show anyone was allowed to try it. Ten years later, there was a faculty show and I was invited to participate. Instead of doing a new piece, and they had changed curators and no one remembered the Gargoyle piece, I just broke the wall open again and exposed it... it's still there. There were beer cans inside the wall because I wanted to make sure that anyone who opened it would see the empty beer cans of the last crew that sheetrocked it over. At the end of the show, I did the same thing. I sheetrocked it over again. I will do the same thing if I ever show up at the Walter McBean again.